

Memorandum.

To: The Clerk to the Committee
Committee on Constitutional, Legal & Parliamentary Affairs,
Office of Parliament,
Osu, Accra,
Ghana.

From: Mr S [REDACTED] A. A [REDACTED]

Date: 30th September 2021

RE: Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights & Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021.

It is with great delight and gratitude that I accept the invitation given by your honourable office to submit this memorandum to assist the Committee in its review and consideration of the “Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021”.

It is my belief that, as long as humans have brains and the capability to exercise their capabilities, we will always have differing views and opinions. But one thing bridges this gap of argument and confusion is the realization and acceptance of factual arguments not based on sentiments but on verifiable facts. The questions to be answered in this memorandum are to tackle the arguments raised by the proposers of this bill and reveal the facts behind the misinformation they have used as a reason for the creation and promotion of this bill.

1. What does LGBTTTQQAAP+ mean?

According to the Macmillan dictionary and urban dictionary, LGBTTTQQAAP means Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Transsexual, Queer, Questioning, Intersex, Asexual, Allies and/or Pansexual.¹ Each of these words has its own meaning and it is as follows:

Lesbian: A woman who is attracted (emotionally, sexually, and physically) only to other women.

¹ Macmillan Dictionary, LGBTTTQQAAP. Sourced
<https://www.macmillandictionary.com/dictionary/british/lgbttqqaap>

Gay: A man who is attracted (emotionally, sexually, and physically) only to other men, but also used to broadly describe people who are attracted to the same sex.

Bisexual: Anyone who is attracted (emotionally, sexually, and physically) to more than one sex/gender.

Transgender: Someone whose gender identity differs from their gender at birth.

Transsexual: Similar to transgender but it refers to people who desire to or have permanently transitioned to the gender with which they identify, seeking medical assistance.

Queer: Reclaimed pejorative term now used by people who don't identify with the binary terms of male and female or gay and straight and do not wish to label themselves by their sex acts.

Questioning: Someone who is still questioning or exploring their sexual/gender identity.

Intersex: Someone who's body is neither fully male or female due to medical variation. Includes people previously known as hermaphrodites, now considered an offensive term.

Ally: Someone who is straight but supports the LGBTTTQQAAP community.

Asexual: Someone with no sexual attraction to any gender.

Pansexual: Someone whose sexual attraction is not based on gender and more based on personality. They may also be gender fluid. Sometimes used to differentiate between the binary choice of two genders implied by "bisexual."²

2. Are these Sexual Orientations a result of Psychological disorder?

The above mentioned sexual orientations are not a choice nor did they come up from a confused state of being, but rather from an understanding of who a person is and how they have been created to express their life in their full glory and purpose.

² The italicized information is derived from the prominent website of Deutsche Welle (DW). Sourced from <https://www.dw.com/en/gay-lesbian-queer-what-is-lgbt-and-lgbttqgiaap/a-45389126>

The American Psychological Association (APA) has unequivocally indicated that Lesbian, gay and Bisexuality are not a mental disorder and as such finds the so called conversion therapies, as ascribed in this bill, a harmful and misguided act that has no scientific (factual) basis to it.³ This will mean that, for a nation to have a law that proposes the usage of unethical, inhumane and non-scientifically proven tool purposed to convert a minority of its population into its subjective definition of what a *“Proper Human Sexual Rights”* ought to be **(as established in Sections 20 and 23 of this Bill)**, then it is apt to declare that state as an oppressive and barbaric state that infringes on the Human Rights of citizens and encroaches on their freedom to attain self-actualisation to play a key role in the development of the nation.

The Sociologist Abraham Maslow in his lectures on Self Actualisation stated that *“...What a man can be, he must be. He must be true to his own nature.”* What this bill proposes is far from being true to one's nature but rather attempts a psychological mutation backed by misguided religious argument and misinformation.

3. Homosexuality in African History:

Before the onset of colonialism and the Abrahamic Religions (*Judaism, Christianity, and Islam*) on the African continent, same-sex relationship has been a normal phenomenon. Prominent examples of this fact is recorded among the priests of the mighty Pharaohs where archaeologist found the burial chamber of a same sex couple who were high officials in the courts of a pharaoh of Egypt (*Nyankh-Khnum and Khnum-hotep - they lived and served under pharaoh Niuserre during the 5th Dynasty*).

The warriors of the great Zulu fighters in South Africa as they transition to manhood are encourage to engage to what they call in their local language as *“hlobonga”* (thigh sex), and in Lesotho they had the instruction of the *“inkotshane”* (Boy wife). King Mwanga of Buganda (now Uganda) was an openly homosexual man and it is on record that the British colonial ambition made them pair with Christians and Muslim groups to depose him of his rulership until he reached an agreement with the British East Africa Company.

In west Africa, the story is not different from all indications! In the Northern part of Nigeria effeminate men were known as *“Yan daudu”* which is a Hausa term and many of these men were considered to be wives of other men. There are several accounts of these across

³ American Psychological Association, their article on Sexual Orientation and Homosexuality. Sourced from <https://www.apa.org/topics/lgbtq/orientation>

Nigeria and based on its proximity to Ghana before colonial border lines, there is no doubt that similar cases existed in Ghana. In Ghana, a prominent example of same sex marriage or partnership will be the “Agɔnwolɛ agyale” which marriage between two persons of the same sex among the Nzema of Ghana.

These are a few examples of the possible mountain of historical information we have lost as a result of our colonial heritage and the introduction of the Abrahamic religions on the continent. There is no doubt on the facts that homosexuality has been a part of the African culture and heritage before Colonialism. The Criminal Offence Acts of 1960 (Act 29, section 98 and 99) that makes reference to sexual intercourse with a person, is a relic of the Cultural distortion of the African under the colonial era. As homosexual relations has been [art of the Ghanaian and African social construct and seen favourable before the pure culture underwent the distortion and demonization as seen under the introduction of the Abrahamic religions and the colonial laws.

The only non-African argument here is to say that homosexuality is non-African, as it is evidential that the opposite is significantly true. And the actual African reality of an African family values also consisted instances of same-sex relationships and marriages.

4. *Setting the Records Straight on Homosexuality and Paedophilia:*

Majority of Child molestations and sexual abuses have been perpetrated by men. Several reports on this topic contradict one another on the statistics of the sexual orientation of these horrible men. If we should use the rule of thumb to argue on sample size, on average homosexuals make up to 3% or 4% of the population which will mean that about 3% of the cases on child molestation and sexual abuse will be perpetrated by homosexuals with the larger figure being committed by heterosexuals. In Ghana, many of the child abuse cases reported are perpetrated by close family relatives or trusted persons who represent themselves as heterosexuals. You find these people in high places of leadership in public, religious organisations, professional settings and also in the normal places of daily livelihood as friends of the family or close acquaintances.

Instead of demonising a sexual minority as being the perpetrators of paedophilia and or child sexual abuses, we should seek to change the culture of handling such cases at home and rather report them to the right institutions for effective recording, provision of assistance to the victims and the prosecution of the aggressors - who in this case is more likely to be heterosexual rather than a homosexual.

The protection of children and the provision of a safe environment for their development should be done in a holistic environment that does not make one's sexual orientation a factor for suspicion and or likelihood of committing such dreadful acts of crime against innocent souls. A person's sexual orientation should not be a factor to determine the severity of punishment to be received under the law or determine the level of watchfulness in the prevention of such crimes. This argument also falls in line with the case against sex traffickers - thus a person's sexual orientation does not determine the gravity or type of crimes they will commit.

5. Discourse on Objective Sex Education Curriculum; Rights to Assemble and Rights to Adoption by LGBT+ Persons:

Section 12 and 13 of the proposed bill will inevitably undermine the establishment of an objective sex education curriculum in the Ghanaian schools. The adolescent child needs to be empowered to understand their sexual development and ways to safely learn about these changes. To pretend that teenagers are not engaged in sexual activities amongst themselves will mean we will be living in a self-imposed state of delusion. These sections of the proposed bill will deny teenagers who identify as LGTB+ the opportunity to understand their sexuality and safely learn about these changes without the negative stigma that is being promoted. The prevention of sexually transmitted diseases such as HIV and AIDS are not a unique problem to homosexuals but also affects heterosexuals. The spread of HIV and AIDS amongst the LGBT+ community is due to the lack of access to sexual education related to their orientation and the provision of safe sex kits to the group. It is in this light that, we should seek to promote an education system that speaks objectively on sex education that will include safe sex topics for LGBT+ youths as well. To preach abstinence without preaching safe sex simultaneously is a recipe to create an environment that breeds sexually transmitted diseases for both heterosexuals and homosexuals alike.

The right to assembly is a key factor in social development and growth of a person as well as in their knowledge acquisition. Section 12, 13, 14, 15 and 16 will prevent LGBT+ persons to build their safe place to learn about themselves and develop key skills that build upon their self-confidence and worth in a society that has demonized them since colonialism and the introduction of the Abrahamic religion on African soil.

Section 17 and 18 touches on areas of adoption and fosterage that relied on grossly distorted facts. On the contrary, research from the University of Melbourne in Australia indicated that children raised by same-sex couples are more happier, more healthy and

performed academically better than their peers raised in heterosexual homes.⁴ It is important to note that the quality of parenting and economic wellbeing of the family outweighs the importance of the sexual orientation of the family the child is raised in.⁵

6. Conclusion:

Ghana's constitution is the supreme law of the land and any other law that undermines the rights and freedoms as enshrined therein is void. It is arguable to claim that the *Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights & Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021* falls under the confines of the constitution of Ghana when it has been clearly laid out that this bill will further undermine the Ghanaian family and cultural values that has existed on the land many years ago, even before the birth of colonialism and the indoctrination of our forefathers to the Abrahamic religions, special mention of Christianity and Islam. As a country governed by the principles as enshrined in the Constitution of Ghana, let us seek to protect, preserve and promote peaceful coexistence amongst ourselves. It suffices to say that, the word homosexuality is a new concept introduced to the Christian Bible for the first time in Germany in 1946. The historical context of the Biblical and Quranic passages do not address same-sex relationships that deal with consenting adults who are in romantic union.⁶ This defeats the arguments on religious grounds against the protection of LGBT+ rights in Ghana.

On the legal and social ramifications globally, this bill will grossly undermine the attainment of Sustainable Development Goals 3 that focuses on **Good health and Well-being**. The bill will seek to promote a state-led discrimination, psychological and physical torture of persons that identify as LGBT+. This in turn breaches the United Nations Human Rights Declarations of which Ghana is a ratified member. Ghana stands to lose more in social development, economic development and international credibility if this bill is passed in the Parliament of Ghana and made into law.

⁴ BMC Public Health, in their research article titled "Parent-reported measures of child health and wellbeing in same-sex parent families: a cross-sectional survey". Sourced from <https://bmcpublihealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1471-2458-14-635>

⁵ The Washington Post, in their report article "Children of same-sex couples are happier and healthier than peers, research shows." Sourced from <https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/morning-mix/wp/2014/07/07/children-of-same-sex-couples-are-happier-and-healthier-than-peers-research-shows/>

⁶ The Conversation, on their journal "The Qur'an, the Bible and homosexuality in Islam". Sourced from <https://theconversation.com/friday-essay-the-quran-the-bible-and-homosexuality-in-islam-61012>